

A NEW STRAIN-BASED TRIANGULAR ELEMENT FOR 2D STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT: *This work presents a novel strain-based finite element formulation specifically designed for the comprehensive analysis of two-dimensional structures under static and dynamic elastoplastic conditions. The proposed triangular element features three degrees of freedom per node, including two in-plane translational components and one rotational component about the normal axis. The displacement field is derived from predefined strain functions that satisfy the compatibility equations, while the interpolation functions are carefully constructed to provide an exact representation of rigid body motions. The developed formulation is applicable to both static and time-dependent elastoplastic analyses. In the static case, the element accurately determines nodal forces, displacements, and stress distributions. For dynamic analyses, a lumped mass matrix combined with an explicit time integration scheme is adopted to improve computational efficiency. The accuracy and robustness of the proposed element are validated through several benchmark test problems, demonstrating its excellent numerical performance and reliability in structural analysis.*

KEYWORDS: *dynamic elastoplastic analysis; strain based approach; triangular element; drilling rotation; lumped mass; elastoplastic analysis*

1 INTRODUCTION

For many structural applications, linear analysis is no longer sufficient to ensure realistic and safe design outcomes. To gain a better understanding of structural behavior, it is essential to account for nonlinear effects, particularly those arising from material inelasticity. Over the past decades, numerous researchers have turned to the strain-based approach to develop improved finite elements, with a primary focus on enhancing their performance. Early efforts in this area were limited to curved elements [1, 2], but the approach was eventually extended to plane elasticity problems [3–10], three-dimensional elasticity [11–13], cylindrical shells [14–17], plate bending [18–23] and shells [24]. Dynamic elastoplastic analysis plays a crucial role in finite element simulations [25–27], especially since exact solutions exist only for a limited number of simple cases. However, conventional displacement-based elements often become inefficient in such analyses, especially in terms of computational cost. In contrast, strain-based

elements have demonstrated superior performance and efficiency across several studies [1–24,31].

In this paper, we introduce a new triangular strain-based finite element called “**SBTE3N**” (Strain-Based Triangular Element with Three Nodes), which incorporates drilling degrees of freedom, specifically designed for static and dynamic elastoplastic analysis. A lumped mass model together with explicit time integration is employed to conduct the analysis. Compared to existing strain-based membrane elements, the proposed SBTE3N demonstrates superior numerical accuracy over all of them, while maintaining a computational efficiency comparable to the Q8 element. The main originality of SBTE3N lies in the introduction of a novel strain field, while its formulation is based on numerical integration, in contrast to SBRIEIR, SBTIEIR, and SBT3, which rely on analytical integration. This difference leads the latter group to deliver only moderate precision, especially for distorted meshes. To validate the proposed element, several numerical examples are presented, demonstrating its accuracy and

effectiveness in linear and dynamic elastoplastic analysis.

2 METHODS

2.1 Formulation of the developed element

Figure 1 presents a schematic representation of the SBTE3N element, a triangular finite element possessing three independent nodal parameters at each corner node: two translational components along the in-plane axes and a rotational degree of freedom about the element's mid-surface.

Fig. 1 SBTE3N element

In a two dimensional, the strain is described by three components;

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x &= U_{,x} \\ \varepsilon_y &= V_{,y} \\ \gamma_{xy} &= U_{,y} + V_{,x} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where: ε_x denotes the bending strain in the x-direction, ε_y represents the bending strain in the y-direction, and γ_{xy} corresponds to the shear strain, and U, V are the displacements in the x and y directions, respectively.

The strain components given in Equation (1) are interdependent since they are defined through the displacement fields U and V. As a result, they are subject to an extra constraint that must be satisfied, the compatibility condition. This constraint is derived by removing the displacement components U and V from Equation (1), resulting in the following expression:

$$\frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_x}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon_y}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 \gamma_{xy}}{\partial x \partial y} = 0 \quad (2)$$

As an initial step, Equation (1) is resolved under the condition of null strain in all directions, allowing us to derive the subsequent relation:

$$\begin{aligned} U &= a_1 - a_3 y \\ V &= a_2 + a_3 x \\ \theta &= a_3 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) defines the three rigid body displacement components. To represent these rigid body motions, we use three independent constants (a_1, a_2, a_3). The remaining six constants (a_4, a_5, \dots, a_9) are used to describe the displacements resulting from the deformation (straining) of the element. These constants are distributed among the strain components as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_x &= a_4 + a_5 y + 2a_9 x \\ \varepsilon_y &= a_6 + a_7 x + a_9 y \\ \gamma_{xy} &= a_8 + a_9 (x^2 + y^2) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The strain components defined in Equation (4) fulfill the compatibility condition stated in Equation (2). These expressions from Equation (4) are set equal to the corresponding expressions involving U and V from Equation(1). The resulting system of equations is then integrated, leading to:

$$\begin{aligned} U &= a_4 x + a_5 xy - a_7 y^2/2 + a_8 y/2 + a_9 (x^2 + y^3/3) \\ V &= a_2 + a_3 x - a_5 x^2/2 + a_6 y + a_7 xy + a_8 x/2 + a_9 (\frac{y^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3}) \\ \theta &= a_3 - a_5 x + a_7 y + a_9 (x^2 - y^2)/2 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The complete displacement functions are derived by combining Equations (3) and (5), resulting in the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} U &= a_1 - a_3 y + a_4 x + a_5 xy - a_7 y^2/2 + a_8 y/2 + a_9 (x^2 + y^3/3) \\ V &= a_2 + a_3 x - a_5 x^2/2 + a_6 y + a_7 xy + a_8 x/2 + a_9 (\frac{y^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3}) \\ \theta &= a_3 - a_5 x + a_7 y + a_9 (x^2 - y^2)/2 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The stiffness matrix $[K^e]$ for the present element is given by:

$$[K^e] = [C]^{-T} \left(\int_{-1}^1 \int_{-1}^1 [Q]^T [D] [Q] \det |J| d\xi d\eta \right) [C]^{-1} \quad (7)$$

Matrices [Q], [J], and [D] represent the strain-displacement relationship, the Jacobian matrix, and the material elasticity respectively. The matrix [C] and [Q] are defined in appendix.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Linear numerical validation

3.1.1 Linear Mac-Neal's test

We examine a slender beam model originally proposed by MacNeal[28]. The geometry of the structure, along with its material properties, is illustrated in Figure 2. The mesh is well structured, and the 4x4 Gaussian integration scheme is used. The corresponding deflection results are presented in Table 1. Analysis of the linear deflection data reveals that the proposed finite element remains unaffected by mesh distortion. For a regular mesh configuration, the computed results closely match the analytical solution. In comparison to the strain-based element, the new element demonstrates superior accuracy under both loading conditions. In computing time it is more economic than the SBQE.

Element	Shear P=1			Bending M=10		
	Regular	Parallel	Trapezoidal	Regular	Parallel	Trapezoidal
SBTIEIR	0.0050	0.0039	0.000054	0.03186	0.02727	0.00108
SBTE3N	0.1081	0.1057	0.1059	0.270	0.268	0.268
SBQE	0.1073	0.1057	0.1058	0.268	0.266	0.267
SBT3	0.1042	0.1026	0.1026	0.267	0.266	0.266
Analytical	0.1081			0.270		

Fig. 2 Mac-Neal and Harder patch tests

Table 1. MacNeal-Harder test: Numerical deflection Results

3.1.2 Plane flexure of cantilever beam

The task concerns the determination of the tip displacement V_A of a cantilever beam having a constant section and subjected to a uniformly distributed transverse load. The material properties are defined by a Young's modulus of 10^7 and a Poisson ratio of 0.3, as illustrated in Figure 3. This benchmark has already been analyzed in [7]. Numerical outcomes for various mesh configurations are compiled in Table 2. The results indicate that the proposed element achieves superior accuracy compared with others numerical models.

Fig. 3 Cantilever beam in plane flexure

Table 2. Displacement at the point A in plane flexure

Mesh	Elements		
	FRQ [7]	SBRIEIR [7]	SBTE3N
(a)	2.76	2.75	2.79
(b)	3.44	3.43	3.51
(c)	3.56	3.56	3.66
Beam Theory $V_A=4.03$			

3.2 Dynamic analysis

3.2.1 Dynamic analysis of a cantilever steel beam

A numerical simulation is conducted on a cantilevered steel beam subjected to a concentrated

impact force of 10 kN applied at its free extremity (refer to Figure 4a). The analysis employs the developed strain finite element formulation incorporating the von Mises yield criteria. The two-dimensional configuration of the beam, depicted in Figure 4a, is meshed using a grid of 18 by 16 triangular elements.

Figures 4b and 4c respectively depict the temporal profile of the applied load and the constitutive stress-strain response of the material. The mechanical properties adopted in the model include a Young's modulus of $E=2 \times 10^5 \text{ N/mm}^2$, a tangent modulus $E_T=0$ (indicating an elastic-perfectly plastic response), a Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.3$, a mass density $\rho=7850 \text{ kg/m}^3$, and a yield strength of $\sigma_0=400 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The reduced Gaussian integration scheme is used in this case. A comparable structural case was previously investigated in reference [27], utilizing linear quadrilateral and three-dimensional hexahedral elements. The evolution of vertical displacement over time at the loading point, as computed via the present element and compared to results from the commercial ANSYS software [29], is compiled in Table 3. The results from the strain based element SBTE3N and ANSYS FEM show excellent agreement.

Fig. 4 (a): Geometry loading and materials of example 1, (b) loading history, (c) stress-strain curve

Table 3. Displacement versus time of the cantilever beam

Time(msec)	Displacement (mm)	
Elements	SBTE3N	Ansys [29]
0.0	0.00	0.00
0.1	0.42	0.42
0.2	1.12	1.12

0.3	1.42	1.42
0.4	1.11	1.12
0.5	0.82	0.84
0.6	1.24	1.25
0.8	1.43	1.44
0.9	1.14	1.15

3.2.2 Forced vibration of elastoplastic solid in plane strain conditions

This test has been treated in ref [30] using the Q8 element as shown in figure 5. All the explicit integration method and lumped mass have been used in this example. The yield stress of VonMises is set to $\sigma_{max} = 50.000$, the Young's modulus $E=3.10^7$, the

Poisson's ratio $\nu=0.3$, the density $\rho=0.7333 \cdot 10^{-3}$, the load multiplier is $P_{ch}=180$, and the number of time step is 700.

Fig. 5 Elastoplastic cantilever beam: Geometry and mesh

Table 4 indicates that the developed triangular strain-based finite element SBTE3N is found numerically very accurate in elastoplastic analysis and it has a rapid convergence to the numerical solution. In computing times it is more economic than the higher order elements.

Table 4. Displacement versus time step of the elastoplastic cantilever beam

Time Step	Displacements at Node 13	
	Q8 [30]	SBTE3N
0	0	0
$0.5000 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$-0.2995 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.3085 \cdot 10^{-3}$
$0.1000 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.1214 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-0.1216 \cdot 10^{-2}$
$0.1500 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.2684 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-0.2685 \cdot 10^{-2}$
$0.2000 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.4867 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-0.4971 \cdot 10^{-2}$
$0.2500 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.8084 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-0.8092 \cdot 10^{-2}$
$0.3000 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.1231 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-0.1241 \cdot 10^{-1}$
$0.3500 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-0.1742 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-0.1749 \cdot 10^{-1}$

0.4000.10 ⁻³	-0.2331.10 ⁻¹	-0.2332.10⁻¹
0.4500.10 ⁻³	-0.2991.10 ⁻¹	-0.3001.10⁻¹
0.5000.10 ⁻³	-0.3724.10 ⁻¹	-0.3718.10⁻¹
0.5500.10 ⁻³	-0.4494.10 ⁻¹	-0.4491.10⁻¹
0.6000.10 ⁻³	-0.5287.10 ⁻¹	-0.5286.10⁻¹
0.6500.10 ⁻³	-0.6113.10 ⁻¹	-0.6099.10⁻¹
0.7000.10 ⁻³	-0.6982.10 ⁻¹	-0.6978.10⁻¹

4 CONCLUSION

This study introduces a novel finite element designated as SBTE3N, constructed within a strain-based formulation for analyzing two-dimensional structures under both static and dynamic elastoplastic conditions. The element features a simple triangular three-node configuration, while integrating higher-order polynomial terms to enhance its performance. Computational experiments performed with the SBTE3N element reveal strong agreement with existing solutions, demonstrating:

- high accuracy in elastic and dynamic elastoplastic analysis.

- Additionally, the element exhibits a rapid convergence rate toward reference solutions across all test cases, making it well-suited for practical engineering applications involving dynamic elastoplastic behavior.

- In distortions configurations, the developed element exhibits excellent results, and can be used in severe cases of distortions.

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$$[Q] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & x & xy & 0 & -y^2/2 & y/2 & x^2 + y^3/3 \\ 0 & 1 & x & 0 & -x^2/2 & y & xy & x/2 & \frac{y^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -x & 0 & y & 0 & (x^2 - y^2)/2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -y & x & xy & 0 & -y^2/2 & y/2 & x^2 + y^3/3 \\ 0 & 1 & x & 0 & -x^2/2 & y & xy & x/2 & \frac{y^2}{2} + \frac{x^3}{3} \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & -x & 0 & y & 0 & (x^2 - y^2)/2 \end{bmatrix}$$

Appendix